

Abstract

The main objective of this study was to investigate the determinants of challenges associated with performance appraisal systems used for assessing cataloguers in Nigerian university libraries. A quantitative research method was employed using a cross sectional research design. The study population comprised all the one hundred and seventy-four (174) heads of cataloguing units in all the universities (including federal, state and private) across Nigeria. The total enumeration method was used to include all 174 heads of cataloguing in the population of the study. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaires was produced on Google form and distributed through social media (Linkedin, Whatsapp, Telegram) and e-mail to the respondents. A total of 171 librarians responded with a response rate of 98%. Collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics with frequencies and percentages computed in tables. Findings of the study revealed that: some of the challenges associated with the performance appraisal system used for assessing cataloguers included, subjectivity and bias, time consuming, inconsistent results, no true test for cataloguers peculiar knowledge, skills and attitude among others; the appraisals for cataloguers should include job requirement areas that are specific to cataloguing, encapsulating the nitty-gritty of knowledge, skills and attitude/behavioral aspects as opposed to the current appraisal which contains mostly general attitudinal/behavioral aspects. The study recommends that: the components of the performance appraisals for assessing cataloguers should cover detailed aspects peculiar to cataloguing job roles/functions; a more scientific appraisal system (such as technologically driven software) that will ensure a more objective and effective assessment of cataloguers should be developed.

Keywords: Challenges, Performance appraisal, Cataloguers Assessment, University Libraries

Introduction

Performance appraisal as a means to manage organisations appears to be enjoying much attention from academics and practitioners, both in the public and private sector in recent years. Performance appraisal is an inevitable and universal responsibility of the human resource development department of every organisation. According to Ogunlana & Oshinaike (2016) performance appraisal assesses an individual's performance against previously agreed work objectives. It serves two functions: it enables management to evaluate an individual's performance in the current job to identify strengths and overcome weaknesses; and it provides information to assist management plan postings, transfers and promotions. In doing so, management is able to compare performance and potential between officers of the same rank.

Performance appraisal should extend individuals' capacities and utilise their maximum capabilities so that there is improved personal performance and relationships; increased job satisfaction to determine motivation; and improved quality of life (Bateman & Snell, 2011). In the absence of a carefully structured system of appraisal, people will tend to judge the work performance of others, including subordinates in an informal and arbitrary way. An efficient performance appraisal must therefore be a systematic review of an individual employee's performance on the job that is used to evaluate the work effectiveness. Performance appraisal must seek to evaluate and re-evaluate the performance of employees in order to enable them to realise their full potential (Armstrong, 2008).

In the university library domain, the evaluation of employee performance is now an increasingly important aspect of performance management procedures. The measurement of units of production and activity has progressed from the measurement of outputs (formation) to the measurement of outcomes (summation) (Van Thiel and Leeuw, 2002; de Vries, 2010).

The university library performance management framework is characterized by the role of employee performance in accomplishing its goal, which is primarily to support teaching and learning activities by providing information resources and services to the academic community, through a systematic procedure involving the selection, acquisition, organisation, preservation and dissemination of information. Empirical studies abound in human resource management from all sectors including librarianship that attribute effective performance appraisals to many important work outcomes, such as improved employee productivity, innovativeness, competency, identifying employee strengths and weaknesses, job satisfaction, commitment and motivation (Curzi, Fabbri, Scapolan, & Boscolo, 2019; Okoye, Mbagwu, Abanum & Nwaohiri, 2019; Idowu, 2017; Agyen- Gyasi & Boateng, 2015; Ikonne, 2015).

Preliminary investigations and information gathered from literature revealed that the appraisal system used in Nigerian University libraries is the Annual Performance Appraisal (APA). The contents of the APA is predominated mostly by behavioral/attitudinal attributes, giving less emphasis to the specific functional, professional knowledge and skills areas, thereby making it too generic. When the technical nature of cataloguing work, which sets it apart from other departments within the library system is considered, one could, without equivocation argue that the general purpose annual appraisal system cannot effectively disclose specifics of knowledge, skills and attitudes possessed by cataloguers, that should allow them to be fit to perform their job functions on one hand and allow room for improvement on the other. Consequently, the general view among cataloguers in the academic libraries is that the appraisal method does not reflect the true measure of individual performance based on the job roles/description being performed (Ikonne, 2015; Agyen-Gyasi and Boateng (2015).

Furthermore, in Nigeria, there seem to be paucity of studies on the problems of the performance appraisal method used on cataloguers in the university libraries. Little is currently known about the micro-analytical approach to cataloguer performance as it affects the macro-strategic approach to organisational performance in Nigerian university libraries. The focus of this study therefore, is to investigate the challenges associated with the appraisal system used for cataloguer performance assessment in Nigerian universities libraries with particular emphasis on the views of the cataloguers on the specific job requirements that should be contained in the instruments for their appraisals.

Statement of the problem

Cataloguers working in Nigerian university libraries hold a most vital position in providing effective description and proper placement of the information contents. They are charged with the responsibility of mitigating the disarray that would have occurred if information resources were not organised. As such they are expected to continuously strive to re-tool re-skill and upgrade competencies to be consistent in the pursuit of professional development and competitive edge (Olayemi & Olayemi, 2019). This is because their work environment is dynamic, wide-ranged and in a constant state of change precipitated by the ever evolving nature of information with the advent of the new technologies to library operations (CILIP, 2020). Thus, it becomes pertinent that cataloguers are continually subjected to assessment by way of appraising their job performance on a regular basis in order to keep developing their skills.

Performance appraisal has been linked to organisations' success as concerns pertaining to the concept are on the increase in university library management circles all over the world (Kanik, 2011). Performance Appraisal in Nigeria is usually done using the APA system. Bearing in mind that one important outcome of performance appraisal is the detection of specific areas of strength and weakness in employees, one can argue that the pursuit of professional development and competitive edge must begin at this point. This can better be achieved when the appraisal is based on specific descriptions of the jobs performed by workers rather than a more general appraisal system.

In Nigeria, university libraries in general and cataloguing department in particular often face challenges on how they can best measure and evaluate the skills, abilities, knowledge and experiences of librarians/cataloguers, particularly when the appraisal exercise does not often reflect the actual work (i.e. the job descriptions) in the unit.

This emanates from the use of APA. The APA has been criticized by Prentice in Okpe (2012) as providing a general assessment that does not address the peculiarities and differences in the activities of the different units in the library.

Furthermore, most of the studies conducted in the area of performance appraisal in Nigeria focused on librarians in general (Okoye, Mbagwu, Abanum & Nwaohiri, 2019; Idowu, 2017; Ikonne, 2015; Okpe, 2012). There is a dearth of studies on performance appraisal as it concerns cataloguers owing to the fact that appraisal can be best achieved when staff are assessed based on the specifics of their job roles. Discussions with heads of cataloguing departments agrees with the findings of **Njoku (2019)** that there is one standard performance appraisal instrument used for the entire library staff, which is developed by the Human Resource Development Departments and therefore too generic in nature to cater for the specific appraisal needs of the various units. It is against this background that this study aims at investigating the determinants of challenges associated with the appraisal methods used with emphasis on identifying specific areas of cataloguing job functions that should be included in the appraisal instruments for cataloguers in Nigerian university libraries.

Objectives of the study

The research objectives for the study are as follows:

1. To identify the challenges associated with the performance appraisal systems used for assessing cataloguers in university libraries in Nigeria.
2. To identify the specific job requirement areas that should be included in the appraisals for cataloguers in libraries under study.

Review of related literature

Determinants of challenges associated with the performance appraisal system used for assessing cataloguers

Performance is usually an ongoing process in libraries. Performance assessment in the library usually starts from the point of University Librarian whose major role is to link the goals of the library to the strategic objectives of the parent institution (Schachter, 2004). One major determinant challenge of the appraisal system used for cataloguers in Nigeria is that it is general in nature and does not reflect the specific job roles performed (Okpe's, 2012). This suggests that the cataloguer competence is never really measured, since the appraisal does not truly test for cataloguers' knowledge, skills and attitudes nor provide feedback to point out areas of strengths and weaknesses in order to encourage continuous learning that will lead to improvement on the job and create the capacity for mentorship. To buttress the view, many scholars (for example; Grote, 2002; Okpe, 2012; Ikonne, 2015; Idowu, 2017; Okoye, Mbagwu Abanum, & Nwaohiri, 2019) agree that annual performance appraisal used in most organisations including university libraries have always been considered problematic and an unwanted management task. It can therefore be inferred that the appraisals do not measure individual workers knowledge, skills, behaviours and traits; not to talk of the job roles actually performed.

According to Prentice in Okpe (2012) "*the appraisal system is a general assessment that does not address the peculiarities and differences in the activities of the different units in the library*". When the technical nature of cataloguing work, which sets it apart from other departments within the library system is considered, one could, without equivocation argue that the general-purpose annual appraisal system cannot effectively disclose specifics of knowledge, skills and attitudes possessed by cataloguers. This is evidenced in Cintrón and Flaniken's (2011) study that provides a detailed look at a population of 108 colleges and universities. Dissatisfaction was found with the appraisal process due to (a) lack of leadership support, (b) supervisors not being held accountable for the timely completion of appraisals, and (c) the lack of training provided to supervisors to conduct performance appraisals well.

The current appraisal methods have not resulted in a significant improvement in the overall performance or productivity of the library employees and cataloguers in particular. Thus, the annual performance appraisal system in Nigeria can be said to be ineffective. Most of the studies done on the challenges of appraisal systems in Nigeria were on the library generally and also did not cover the entire university system in terms of scope. This study thus, filled that gap to determine the challenges of performance appraisal used specifically for cataloguers in Nigerian university libraries including the federal, state and private.

Job requirements/areas for appraising cataloguers in libraries

The job requirement areas that should be appraised in cataloguers are broadly categorized into three namely: knowledge; skills and; attitude (Association for Library Collections and Technical Services, 2017; Kyndt & Baert, 2015; Soutter, 2013; Singer & Griffiths, 2010). Knowledge areas include professional aspects such as cataloguing, classification, indexing, abstracting and subject analysis. This can further be broken down into cataloguers knowledge of: cataloguing standards like AACR2, RDA; cataloguing tools like classification structures and schemes, subject heading lists; cataloguing principles like Ranganathan's laws of librarians, principles of authority control, principles behind controlled vocabularies; systems and technology in library management like knowledge of: indexing techniques and database structures, various approaches for metadata creation and library management systems, data standardization i.e. content, structure, data encoding format and exchange and conceptual models for library data like FRBR, FRAD, RDF; structure standards like MARC and Dublin Core; subject analysis procedures (ALCTS, 2017).

In a different view, the Federal Library and Information Center Committee (FLICC) (2011) stated that cataloguers and metadata practitioners (as they are called these days) are expected to be conversant and demonstrate knowledge of: established local, national and international standards and protocols to catalog and classify library materials and resources; established local, national and international standards and protocols for metadata and/or other content structuring systems; tagging to incorporate customer input into library content management structures and; new developments in content organisation and structure. Inferably, understanding those standards would expose cataloguers to the world of digital cataloguing environment and help them appreciate the enormous changes and advancements that accompany it.

Skill areas include professional skills and technological skills. Professional skills comprise cataloguers' ability to catalog, classify, index, abstract, perform subject analysis and other related tasks. Cataloguers have to master cataloguing principles and be skilled in the application of conceptual frameworks, standards and principles used by the library. For example, they have to be skilled in: the use of RDA and AACR2 in the formulation of a consistent cataloguing data and authorized catalogue entries; applying universal standards to local needs; cataloguing and classifying materials using DDC, LC accurately; indexing information; using lists of subject heading like the LC and Sear's lists and; analyzing information contents. Technological skills include cataloguers' ability to apply ICTs and other related cataloguing tools in the conduct of their work (Sokari, Gama, Haliru, Olayemi & Yemi-Peters, 2017). This entails their ability to: use MARC, HTML, XML and metadata schemas like Dublin Core and similar schema; manipulate OPACs; adapt models such as FRBR, RDF and FRAD to library data; use bibliographic databases, library management systems and institutional repositories; create, analyse, edit, evaluate and transform metadata; encode machine readable data and convert records from one metadata schema to another; search internet and database; design web pages; use OCLC bibliographic formats and standards; use Library of Congress-Program for Cooperative Cataloguing Policy Statements (LC-PCC PSs); use Library of Congress Name Authorities; use CONSER Cataloguing Manual (for Serials) (Sung, 2013).

Attitude is demonstrated as functional and behavioral skills that differentiates a superior performer from others. Functional skills include cataloguers' ability to apply consistency, flexibility, judgment, and adaptation in the process of performing their jobs, while behavioral skills include areas such as ability to communicate, meta competence (ability to learn and re-learn), punctuality, capacity to work under pressure, soberness, adherence to rules, sense of urgency, initiative, commitment to duty, neatness and appearance, integrity and trustworthiness, ability to learn quickly, ability to comply with lawful instructions, relationship with public & colleagues, dependability, attitude to work, efficiency and productivity.

Cataloguers can be appraised based on specialized knowledge and skills they possess (from a combination of schooling and working experience) as well as attitudes that are specifically attributed to cataloguing and related tasks (classification, indexing, abstracting). As such, all the job requirement areas earlier mentioned should be included in the appraisal system of cataloguers in order to justify their appraisal process and; provide opportunity for self-management that would result in a continual improvement on the job and; provide capacity for mentorship.

Research methodology

Quantitative research method was employed for the study. The survey research design was considered most appropriate because the design was suitable for collecting cross-sectional data as it is the case for this study. The study population comprised all the one hundred and seventy-four (174) heads of cataloguing units in all the universities (including federal, state and private) across Nigeria. The heads of cataloguing units were chosen because they were likely to be most conversant with the appraisal of subordinate cataloguers and how they could benefit from the study. Census/total enumeration method was used to include all 174 heads of cataloguing in the population of the study, since it was a manageable size. Also, adopting the census method ensured a well representative nature of the population and enabled the objectives of the study to be attained. The researchers were able to make generalisations with regards to the findings of the study. A semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study (data collection instrument). The questionnaires were produced on Google forms and were distributed through the social media (LinkedIn, WhatsApp, Telegram) and e-mail to the respondents. The data was collected on-line for several reasons: reduced cost in terms of logistics; it eliminated problems associated with geographical boundaries and; provided higher response rates. A total of 171 librarians responded with a response rate of 98%. Collected data was analysed using descriptive statistics with frequencies and percentages computed in tables.

Data presentation and analysis

Table 1: Challenges associated with performance appraisal system used for assessing cataloguers in University libraries, Nigeria

Table 1 [see overleaf] shows that majority 170 (99.4%) of respondents agreed that the appraisal system in use for cataloguers does not truly test for peculiar cataloguer knowledge and does not provide capacity for mentoring/mentorship. This is followed by 169 (98.8%) as reflected by the responses on the appraisal system being overly subjective and prone to appraiser biases; does not show the relationship between cataloguer competence and work performance; and does not encourage continuous learning. The least responses were 141 (82.5%) and 144 (84.2) where the respondents agreed that the appraisal system was time consuming and does not provide feedback to the cataloguers respectively.

Table 1: Challenges associated with performance appraisal system used for assessing cataloguers in University libraries, Nigeria

Variables	Freq.	(%)
It is overly subjective and prone to appraiser biases	169	98.8
It is time consuming	141	82.5
Results are often inconsistent & unreliable	155	90.6
It does not truly test for peculiar cataloguer knowledge	170	99.4
It does not truly test for peculiar cataloguer skills and capabilities	164	95.9
It does not truly test for peculiar cataloguer attitudes	158	92.4
It does not show the relationship between cataloguer competence and work performance	169	98.8
It does not encourage continuous learning	169	98.8
It does not provide feedback to the cataloguers	144	84.2
It does not identify areas of strengths and weaknesses of cataloguers	168	98.2
It does not show cataloguers productivity ratings/levels	165	96.5
It does not provide capacity for mentoring/mentorship	170	99.4

Table 2: Specific job requirements that should be included in the appraisals for cataloguers in libraries under study

Variables	Freq.	%
Knowledge Areas		
Knowledge of cataloguing standards like AACR2, RDA	170	99.4
Knowledge of cataloguing tools (like classification structures and schemes, subject heading lists)	167	97.7
Knowledge of cataloguing principles like Ranganathan's laws of librarians, principles of authority control, principles behind controlled vocabularies	170	99.4
Knowledge of systems and technology in library management like indexing techniques and database structures; various approaches for metadata creation; library management systems; data standardization i.e. content, structure, data encoding format and exchange and conceptual models for library data FRBR, FRAD, RDF	161	94.2
Knowledge of structure standards like MARC and Dublin Core	154	90.1
Knowledge of subject analysis procedures	163	95.3
Knowledge of established local, national and international standards and protocols to catalog and classify library materials and resources	149	87.1
Knowledge of established local, national and international standards and protocols for metadata and/or other content structuring systems	147	86.0
Knowledge of new developments in content organisation and structure	168	98.2
Skills areas		
Ability to catalog, classify, index, abstract and perform subject analysis	171	100.0
Ability to apply conceptual frameworks, standards and principles used for cataloguing such as RDA and AACR2 in the formulation of a consistent cataloguing data and authorized catalogue entries	165	96.5
Ability to apply universal standards to local needs	166	97.1
Ability to catalog and classify materials using DDC, LC accurately	170	99.4
Ability to index information	165	96.5
Ability to use lists of subject heading like the LC and Sear's lists	166	97.1
Ability to analyze information contents	169	98.8
Ability to apply ICTs and other related cataloguing tools in the conduct work	170	99.4
Ability to use MARC, HTML, XML and metadata schemas like Dublin Core and similar schema	161	94.2
Ability to manipulate OPACs	166	97.1
Ability to adapt models such as FRBR, RDF and FRAD to library data	165	96.5
Ability to use bibliographic databases, library management systems and institutional repositories	166	97.1
Ability to create, analyse, edit, evaluate and transform metadata	142	83.0
Ability to encode machine readable data and convert records from one metadata schema to another	158	92.4
Ability to search internet and database	167	97.7
Ability to design web pages	133	77.8
Ability to use online cataloguing tools such as LC online, OCLC and classification web	167	97.7
Ability to use Library of Congress-Program for Cooperative Cataloguing Policy Statements (LC-PCC PSs)	155	90.6
Ability to use CONSER Cataloguing Manual for Serials	159	93.0
Attitude areas		
Ability to apply functional skills such as consistency, flexibility, judgment, and adaptation	170	99.4
Ability to apply behavioral skills such as communication, meta competence punctuality, work under pressure, soberness, adhere to rules, sense of urgency, initiative, commit to duty, integrity and trustworthiness, learn quickly, comply with lawful instructions, relate with public & colleagues, dependability, positive attitude to work, efficient and productive.	168	98.2

In area of knowledge areas, table 2 shows that majority of respondents 170 (99.4%) agreed that knowledge of cataloguing principles like Ranganathan's laws of librarians and knowledge of cataloguing standards like AACR2, RDA should be included in the appraisal assessment system. This is followed by 168 (98.2%) that is Knowledge of new developments in content organisation and structure. In areas of skills, the most response 171 (100.0%) went for ability to catalog, classify, index, abstract and perform subject analysis while 170 (98.4%) went for ability to apply ICTs and other related cataloguing tools in the conduct work and ability to catalog and classify materials using DDC, LC respectively. Respondents also agreed that functional skills 170 (99.4%) and behavioral skills 168 (98.2%) should be included in appraisal for cataloguers.

Discussion of findings

Findings revealed that appraisal system for cataloguers is bedeviled with following challenges: no true test for peculiar cataloguers' knowledge, skills and attitude; lack of capacity for mentoring/mentorship; overly subjective and prone to appraiser biases; does not show the relationship between cataloguer competence and work performance; does not encourage continuous learning; it is time consuming and; does not provide feedback to the cataloguers. This is in line with other studies that agreed that the current performance appraisal systems used for the cataloguers are incompatible with precepts and demands of providing adequate assessment of employees based on their specific performance in job roles (Okpe, 2012; Ikonne, 2015; Idowu, 2017; Okoye, Mbagwu, Abanum, & Nwaohiri, 2019).

Appraisals are supposed to serve as basis for transforming behaviors towards more improved and productive work habits, providing the foundations for evidence-based decision making, where it concerns staff development. Many researches on performance appraisal are of the opinion that most performance appraisal systems in use do not augur well for employee growth in the workplace. In a similar vein, Grint (2007) in the critique of performance appraisal points out that "*its subjectivity – leads to a fruitless search for ever more objective appraisal criteria that is illusory. The consequence need not be that appraisals should be abandoned but they should be treated with much more skepticism and reflexivity*". The appraisal method for assessing cataloguers in Nigeria university libraries should therefore, encapsulate all that is required in order to provide for a holistic and in-depth appraisal owing to the important function/role that cataloguers perform within the larger library setting.

Regarding the identification of specific job requirement areas that should be included in the appraisals for cataloguers, the majority of the respondents agreed that appraisals should include the nitty-gritty of knowledge, skills and attitude/behavioral aspects of cataloguing, such as: knowledge of cataloguing principles like Ranganathan's laws of librarians; knowledge of cataloguing standards like AACR2, RDA; knowledge of new developments in content organization structure; ability to catalogue, classify, index, abstract and perform subject analysis; ability to apply ICTs and other related cataloguing tools; ability to catalogue and classify materials using DDC and LC. This is opposed to the current appraisal which contains mostly general attitudinal/behavioral aspects. Scholars agreed that appraisals for cataloguers should be done based on areas of knowledge, skills and attitude all of which comprise series of cataloguing activities that culminates to mould up a better cataloguer (Association for Library Collections and Technical Services, 2017; Kyndt & Baert, 2015; Sortter, 2013; Singer & Griffiths, 2010).

Conclusion

The need for continuous learning in the workplace is now at the heart of human resource management thus, establishing a foundation for new philosophies in employee assessment that directly/indirectly serves as a basis for re-evaluating employee performance appraisal becomes pertinent. To put it succinctly, among other issues, the finding reveals that the present performance appraisal from the perspective of cataloguer does not match skill sets with specific job roles. From these results, it can therefore, be inferred that the appraisal system does not satisfy its purpose and should be thoroughly improved upon to match with the required peculiarity and specificity of the cataloguing operationality.

Paramount among the aims of performance appraisal is to improve the cataloguers' performance – as a result of the appraisal, the management of the university library should get a better understanding of cataloguer strengths and weaknesses, which would in turn help in learning about areas where their cataloguing capacity could be improved; identify areas where cataloguers need training; enhance productivity; job satisfaction and motivation among the cataloguers and; build a formidable team that will ensure that cataloguing unit contributes in realising the goals of the library and that of the university at large.

Recommendations:

1. The components of the performance appraisals for assessing cataloguers should cover detailed aspects peculiar to cataloguing job roles/functions, apart from the general attitudinal/behavioral aspects contained in the current system in use. These details should include the areas of knowledge, skills and attitude that are specific to cataloguing functions. This is in order to justify the appraisal exercise and to obtain a more objective evaluation of cataloguers, which will result in a continual improvement on job performance and in grooming expert cataloguers over time in line with best practices.

2. A more scientific appraisal system that will ensure a more objective and effective assessment of cataloguers should be developed. This could be in form of a technologically driven system such as software to cater for that purpose

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Zainab Abba Haliru
Department of Library & Information Sciences
Bauchi State University, Gadau, Nigeria
Zahalirui963@gmail.com

Victoria Sokari
University Library
Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria
visokari.lib@buk.edu.ng

Ibrahim Wada
Department of Library & Information Sciences
University of Maiduguri, Nigeria
ibrahimwada@unimaid.edu.ng

Book Review: *Linked Data for the Perplexed Librarian* by Scott Carlson, Cory Lampert, Darnelle Melvin, and Anne Washington. Chicago: ALA Editions, 2020. xi, 164 p. ISBN 978-0-8389-4746-3 (paper).

Reviewed by Christine Megowan, Rare Books Cataloguer, Cardiff University

Linked Data for the Perplexed Librarian by Scott Carlson, Cory Lampert, Darnelle Melvin, and Anne Washington provides a painless introduction to the concepts of linked data and the semantic web, aimed at library staff with little or no technical expertise. Its stated goal is to “present basic information about linked data in a clear, jargon-minimized way” (p. x). For the most part it succeeds in making linked data seem friendly and approachable, with just a few minor caveats.

The book begins with a brief history of the internet and the development of the semantic web, discussing the potential that linked data pioneers like Tim Berners-Lee envisioned and the extent to which it has (or has not) lived up to that potential. From there, the authors use a hypothetical collection of funk and soul vinyl records to illustrate how the information in and about those records can be expressed in ways that computers can interpret and analyse, and which can be enriched by linking to other published datasets. After a whistle-stop tour of some existing linked data projects like WikiData and VIAF, the book points the reader to tools like MarcEdit and OpenRefine which can be used to enhance existing data, and suggests a series of activities that libraries can undertake in preparation for creating their own linked data projects.

At a slim 164 pages, it is not a user’s manual with specific instructions, but instead gently introduces the reader to what linked data is, the types of structures it relies on, and its potential for improving access to library and other cultural heritage collections. It explains much of the technological jargon surrounding BIBFRAME, RDF, SPARQL, and the like in simple terms, enabling the reader to extract more value from the plethora of conference papers, journal articles, and webinars that have been produced around the concept of linked data over the past decade or more. Although the absence of step-by-step guides may frustrate some readers, this focus on high-level concepts has the benefit of increasing the book’s longevity. Where a more specific guide would become increasingly outdated with every new software update, these high-level concepts should remain applicable for the foreseeable future.

While the book does not dwell at length on specific encoding schemas, it does assume that readers have (or are willing to obtain from some other source) sufficient understanding of programming syntax to be able to interpret examples using SQL, JSON, and XML. Staff with no programming experience at all may wish to familiarise themselves with at least the basics of XML in order to get the most out of the middle chapters of this book.

Unlike some linked data evangelists, the authors offer a frank and honest assessment of the past and present barriers to wider application of linked data. The issue of legacy data is addressed indirectly through a discussion of MARC’s history and shortcomings in the context of the semantic web. The real-world examples of linked data in chapter five are dominated by private corporations like Facebook and Google who are often reluctant to share the inner workings of their products. The activities in chapter seven emphasise the importance of having IT support, and the epilogue (aptly titled “The Unprovable Pudding”) acknowledges that an absence of software developers in libraries has prevented many linked data experts from implementing their own research outcomes. While there is no neat and tidy solution to these problems, the authors hope that by equipping more librarians with the vocabulary and understanding to better articulate our technological needs and potential outcomes, the route toward implementing linked data in our everyday work will become clearer.

Bearing these caveats in mind, this book is nevertheless a good introduction to the big picture of what linked data is and how it has the potential to enhance the work already being done by libraries and other cultural heritage institutions. The language and examples are clear and easy to understand and give the reader the confidence to explore further on their own. It gives the reader a sense of the major landmarks in the linked data landscape, with the expectation that they will chart their own path and seek out additional skills and resources in accordance with their specific local needs.

This book is available from: <http://www.ala.org/alcts/resources>

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Submissions: In the first instance, please contact the Co-editors:

Karen Pierce: PierceKF@Cardiff.ac.uk

Philip Keates: p.keates@kingston.ac.uk

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